

ISic1423

I.Sicily inscription 1423

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Necropolis via Androne

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333362

1. □ □ □
2. ἐνθάδε κείττε ²⁶κείτε = κείται²⁶ □
3. ἀεὶ παρθένος ὀ-
4. νόματι Θεοδούλη ζή-
5. σασα [ἔ]τη κβ' □ τελευτᾷ τῇ
6. πρὸ γ' καλ (ανδῶν) □ Ἰανουαρίων,
7. ἐδόθη δὲ ἡ ἔνβασις κατὰ δωρε-
8. ἀν σφραγίδος τῆς πρεσβυτέ (ρας) .
- 9.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644973
EDCS 41300022
EDCS 64900779
PHI 333362

Bibliography

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